

**PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION SKILLS OF HEADS, SERVICE DELIVERY,
AND MEMBERS' TRUST AND CONFIDENCE IN SOCIAL
SECURITY SYSTEM SANTA ROSA BRANCH**

Grace R. Velasco

Laguna College of Business and Arts, Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13765015>

ABSTRACT

The Social Security System (SSS) is a crucial element of social security in the Philippines, where maintaining high standards of service delivery and effective public administration skills is essential for ensuring member trust, confidence, and satisfaction. To explore this, a study was conducted on the SSS Santa Rosa Branch, focusing on the relationship between public administration skills, service delivery, and members' trust and confidence. Utilizing a quantitative research design with a descriptive-correlational approach, the study surveyed heads, employees, and clients. The results demonstrated a significant positive correlation between the level of public administration skills and members' trust and confidence, rejecting the null hypothesis. Similarly, the study found that improved service delivery also positively influenced members' trust and confidence. These findings underscore that higher public administration skills and better service delivery contribute to greater member trust and satisfaction. In light of these results, an action plan was developed to enhance both public administration skills and service delivery at the SSS Santa Rosa Branch, aiming to further improve member trust and confidence in the system. This proactive approach is intended to address identified gaps and support continuous improvement in service quality and member satisfaction.

Keywords: *SSS, service delivery, public administration skills, trust and confidence*

INTRODUCTION

Public administration encompasses a range of administrative functions vital for bolstering and sustaining societies across nonprofit organizations, as well as local, state, and federal governmental levels. It includes tasks such as managing labor relations and ethics, navigating legislative affairs, overseeing public policy, handling financial matters, and orchestrating public budgeting procedures. Public administration cannot exist outside of its political context. Its public nature stems from this environment, which also sets it apart from private or corporate administration. Public administration has established ethical norms and ideals as a career. It has no value as an activity, though. It just represents the societal conventions, ideologies, and power structures. Since a state's function is public administration, it is both established by and constrained by a legal framework (Shafritz et al., 2022).

The same is true with the Philippine Public Administration in government offices is adhered to and includes the Social Security System. In the Philippines, the Social Security System (SSS) administration is guided by a mission, vision, and corporate values that underscore its commitment to providing financial stability and social justice to its members and their families. The SSS endeavors to promote universal coverage and equitable social protection in times of contingencies by providing benefits such as sickness, maternity, disability, retirement, funeral, death, and unemployment benefit through exemplary service delivery, embodying core values of trust, empowerment, and teamwork. Embracing digitalization initiatives, the SSS has made significant strides in enhancing service quality, evident in the proliferation of electronic functionalities such as online filing of loans and benefits thru my.sss, Self-Service Express Terminals, mobile app, and e-centers in SSS branches and barangay e-centers. These can only be realized through proper public administration skills manifested by SSS heads.

The exponential increase in mobile app downloads, 39,831,527 and MY.SSS registrations, 18,581,880 as of December 023 (CPPD Management Reports, 2024), underscore the organization's commitment to accessibility and member convenience. Efforts to address member concerns have resulted in a drastic reduction in complaints, earning recognition from the Civil Service Commission for exemplary complaint resolution rates. Upholding principles of good governance, the SSS has pursued ISO certifications for several branches and currently preparing for an agency-wide ISO certification for all core processes this 2024. It is noteworthy to mention that SSS received accolades from regional and international bodies for innovative projects like the Expanded Maternity Law implementation, Real Time Processing of Contributions Program, E-center sa Barangay, and SSS on-wheels. The recent launch of a Pilot Digital Branch in San Pedro, Laguna, reflects the SSS's commitment to digital transformation, ensuring that members and pensioners receive personalized guidance in utilizing online services. Through such initiatives, the SSS continues to evolve, striving to provide seamless, world-class social security services to its constituents across the Philippines. SSS was one of the recipients of the recently concluded 2024 People's Choice Stevie Awards for Favorite Companies. The 2024 Asia-Pacific Stevie Awards have recognized organizations in 25 markets

including Australia, Cambodia, mainland China, Hongkong SAR, Estonia, India, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Malaysia, New Zealand, Philippines, Singapore, Taiwan, Thailand, the United Kingdom, the United States, and Vietnam (Del Signore, 2024). Given the right public administration skills of the heads, these services can be delivered properly.

Meanwhile, Uzir et al. (2021) also discussed that service quality was an important feature of government services like SSS since it directly influenced trust and faith in the government, and citizen satisfaction played a significant role in developing citizen loyalty to government services. In the globalization trend, government leadership and service quality supplied, in addition to affecting government performance, were critical to a country's competitive edge. Aside from enforcing public authority, public sectors must deliver service quality that meets people's expectations.

The Social Security System (SSS) plays a crucial role in providing meaningful protection to its members and beneficiaries, offering benefits and privileges that contribute to socio-economic development through livelihood programs and loans extended to various entities like corporations, cooperatives, and small to medium-scale entrepreneurs the SSS actively participates in fostering economic growth. Moreover, the SSS demonstrates prudence in managing its funds, considering factors like liquidity and high-yielding interest rates for investments.

Established in 1957 by Republic Act 1161, also known as the Social Security Act of 1954, the Philippine Social Security System served as a vital social insurance program for workers in the private, professional, and informal sectors. Subsequent amendments, such as Republic Act No. 8282 in 1997, and Republic Act 11199 in 2018, further refined its operations. However, it is important to note that while the SSS covers private employees, government workers are under a separate pension fund managed by the Government Service Insurance System (GSIS).

In evaluating the quality of service provided by the SSS, attention is drawn to the importance of public administration skills, service delivery, and the trust and confidence of its members. Recognizing that service quality is paramount for citizen satisfaction and faith in government institutions, there's a growing emphasis on enhancing customer service and responsiveness within the SSS.

Efforts to improve service quality are not only imperative for citizen satisfaction and happiness but also contribute to the country's competitive edge in a globalized world. Governments must prioritize leadership and service quality to meet citizens' expectations effectively. Service quality encompasses various dimensions, including efficiency in processing claims, responsiveness to inquiries, and overall member satisfaction.

Despite its pivotal role, the SSS still faced criticisms regarding its performance, particularly concerning processing delays and payment issues, as highlighted by the Commission on Audit (COA). Challenges such as slow processing of benefits, despite computerization, underscoring the need for continuous improvement and accountability within the organization (Castillo, 2013 as cited in Reyes et al., 2023)

While the SSS serves as a cornerstone of social security in the Philippines, ensuring high-quality service delivery and effective public administration skills remains essential for maintaining trust, confidence, and satisfaction among its members and beneficiaries. Continuous efforts to address shortcomings and enhance service standards are vital for the SSS to fulfill its mandate effectively in the evolving socio-economic landscape. This prompted the researcher to conduct this study regarding public administration skills of heads, service delivery and member's trust and confidence in Social Security System Santa Rosa Branch and developed an action plan as an output.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study was to determine the public administration skills of heads, service delivery, and members' trust and confidence in the Social Security System Santa Rosa Branch. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of manifestation of public administration skills among heads of SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by employees and members in terms of:
 - 1.1 vision and commitment,
 - 1.2 philosophy,
 - 1.3 excellent leadership skills, and
 - 1.4 customer service?
2. What is the service delivery level in SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by clients and employees in terms of:
 - 2.1 accuracy of service,
 - 2.2 perceived quality,
 - 2.3 prompt feedback,
 - 2.4 physical safety, and
 - 2.5 comfortability?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of public administration skills and service delivery in SSS Santa Rosa Branch?
4. What is the SSS Santa Rosa Branch members' trust and confidence in public administration on its services in terms of:
 - 4.1 assurance,
 - 4.2 empathy,
 - 4.3 reliability,
 - 4.4 responsiveness, and
 - 4.5 tangibility?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of public administration skills and members' trust and confidence in SSS Santa Rosa Branch?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the service delivery and members' trust and confidence on SSS Santa Rosa Branch?
7. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

Presents the methods in conducting the study. It includes an in-depth analysis of the research design, sampling design and selection of respondents, data gathering instrument, validation of instrument, data gathering procedures and statistical treatment of the current study.

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design using the descriptive correlational approach. According to Simon (2012, as cited in Pastrana, 2022), the descriptive-correlational approach was a research strategy that entailed monitoring and summarizing a subject's behavior without modifying factors. It was concerned with detecting links and patterns between variables using statistical studies such as correlation coefficients. This method was especially beneficial when researchers wanted to investigate relationships between variables or explain a phenomenon without changing it. This design was utilized to assess the level of manifestation of public administration skills of SSS heads, service delivery, and members' trust and Confidence in the Social Security System Santa Rosa Branch.

Research Locale

The research locale for this study was the SSS Santa Rosa Branch located at 3rd Floor Robinsons Place, Tagapo, Santa Rosa City, Laguna, Philippines. The research was conducted in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch for easy administration in data gathering and due to the accessibility of the respondents.

Population and Sampling

The population of this study was composed of the heads, employees, and clients/members of the SSS Santa Rosa Branch. Thus, this study used stratified random sampling in the selection of respondents. Specifically, the G-power computation was employed to ensure the right number of respondents needed. G*Power, according to Verma and Verma (2020), was a general power analysis program, which was meant to determine the sample size and analyze power in research studies.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the heads, employees, and SSS clients/members of the SSS Santa Rosa Branch. The respondents in this study provided a more complete picture of the level of manifestation of public administration skills of SSS heads, service delivery, and members' trust and confidence in the Social Security System Santa Rosa Branch. The table provided the respondents.

Table A

Respondents of the Study

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Employees	14	2.65%
Clients/Members	515	97.35%
Total	529	100%

The heads, employees, and clients/members were the respondents of this study. The Branch Head, Section Head, and Team Head of the SSS Santa Rosa Branch (14 or 2.65%). While the clients/members were 515 or 97.35%. Groups were included in the study to provide diverse perspectives and improve the external validity of the research.

Instrument

To collect quantitative data from respondents for this study, a researcher-made questionnaire inspired by the survey questionnaire from the study of Deada (2020) was employed. Respondents were asked to rate their level of manifestation of public administration abilities of SSS Heads, Service Delivery, and Members' Trust and Confidence in the Social Security System at the Santa Rosa Branch using a Likert scale. The survey questionnaire was pre-tested to ensure its validity and reliability, and any changes that were required were implemented.

Likert Scale Interpretation
Level of Manifestation of Public Administration skills

Assigned Points	Numerical Range	Categorical Interpretation (CI)	Verbal Interpretation (VI)
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Fully Manifested
3	2.50 – 3.25	Agree	Moderately Manifested
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree	Slightly Manifested
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Not Manifested

The test used Four-point Likert scale which is answerable by Fully Manifested, Moderately Manifested, Slightly Manifested, and Not Manifested to measure the level of manifestation of Public Administration skills among heads of SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by employees in terms of vision and commitment, philosophy, excellent leadership skills and customer service.

Meanwhile, the level of service delivery in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by members/clients in terms of accuracy of service, availability of service, prompt feedback, physical safety, and comfortability were rated as Fully Satisfied, Satisfied, Moderately Satisfied, and Not Satisfied.

Likert Scale Interpretation Level of Service Delivery

Assigned Points	Numerical Range	Categorical Interpretation (CI)	Verbal Interpretation (VI)
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3	2.50 – 3.24	Agree	High
2	1.75 – 2.49	Disagree	Low
1	1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Validation of the Instrument

The research instrument of this study was validated by research professionals and experts with considerable subject matter expertise in the topic. Also, this survey questionnaire underwent pilot testing and was run initially from the same variety of respondents to measure internal consistency before distributing it to the actual participants, which was accomplished through pilot testing. The dependability and consistency of the instrument's internal data were evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha.

The study employed both content validity and expert validity to assess the psychometric soundness of the guide questions. The content validity index that was calculated was 1.00. Lawshe (1975, cited in Catam, 2022) defined content validation as the process of causing an instrument, such as a scale, questionnaire, or checklist, to evaluate the material that it was designed to measure. One method for obtaining content validity was to apply the content validity ratio after a group of subject matter experts assessed the importance of specific sections inside an instrument. The specialists who dedicated their time and effort to considering all the important problems that should be described and clarified in the study process validated and approved this instrument.

These specialists were the statistician for the study, a professor from LCBA, a Corporate Executive Officer from SSS, a Doctor of Public Administration, and the Research Director. As a result, each comment and proposal received thorough attention. Based on proportion relevance, the calculation concluded that CVR met the satisfactory level of 1.0. Hence, the scale of the questionnaire has achieved a satisfactory level of content validity.

Data Gathering Procedure

This study data collection procedure included multiple steps. First, approval from the Head of Luzon South-I Division was obtained to perform the study within the organization. Following acceptance, the specified heads, staff, and clients/members were identified as the study's respondents/participants. Based on the study's research goals and objectives, a researcher-made Likert scale instrument in the form of a survey questionnaire was utilized. The survey questionnaire was pre-tested to ensure its validity and reliability, and any changes that were required were implemented. The survey questionnaire was distributed in person to respondents/participants using a face-to-face

platform. The responses were gathered and encoded before being entered into a database for analysis. The quantitative data from the survey questionnaire was analyzed using mean, frequency, rank, and Pearson r. Finally, the findings were compiled into a report and distributed to SSS Santa Rosa Branch, where recommendations were made to improve the application of public administration skills of SSS Heads, Service Delivery, and Members' Trust and Confidence in the Social Security System.

Ethical Considerations

Throughout the investigation, the research ensured that ethical issues were followed. The study's goals and objectives were communicated to the respondents. They were not required to participate in the survey if doing so was against their desire. Furthermore, the questionnaires that have been collected contained important information relevant to the study's conduct. The work of several writers that were used in this study was correctly referenced, cited, and quoted. Because this study included human respondents, ethical considerations have been considered to safeguard their safety, privacy, and rights.

To appropriately observe and implement the rules of Republic Act 10173 (Data Privacy Act of 2012), an agreement was sought from the participants after explaining the study's aim, process, and their right to withdraw from the study. Confidentiality and anonymity were further assured by assigning codes to the participants' responses and ensuring that no identifiable information was captured. The study followed research ethics guidelines, such as limiting risks to participants, delivering benefits, and guaranteeing equitable treatment of all participants. Before beginning the research, the Institutional Review Board (IRB) gained ethical approval.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

The following were the statistical treatments applied in the study using SPSS:

1. Simple mean was used to determine the respondents' level of the implementation of public administration skills of SSS heads, service delivery, and members' trust and confidence in the Social Security System Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by the respondents of the study. Likert Scale was utilized as an ordered scale from which respondents choose one option that best aligns with their view. It was used to measure respondents' attitudes by asking the extent to which they agree or disagree with a particular question or statement with the level of the implementation of public administration skills of SSS heads, service delivery, and members' trust and confidence in the Social Security System Santa Rosa Branch.

2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was employed to determine a significant relationship between the level of the implementation of public administration skills of SSS heads, service delivery, members' trust and confidence, and the relationship between service delivery and members' trust and confidence in Social Security System Santa Rosa Branch.

Interpretation and Analysis of Data Gathered

The study attempts to determine the Public Administration Skills, Service Delivery, and Members' Trust and Confidence in the Social Security System, Santa Rosa Branch.

Research Question 1:

What is the level of manifestation of public administration skills among the heads of SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by employees and members in terms of:

1.1 Vision

Table 1.1

Level of Manifestation of Public Administration Skills among Heads of SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by Employees and Clients in terms of Vision.

Indicators	X	VI
The Branch Head and Supervisors of SSS Santa Rosa is. . .		
1. Actively involved in communicating a clear and inspiring vision for the branch.	3.89	FM
2. Consistently demonstrates a strong commitment to the mission and goals of the organization.	3.93	FM
3. Effectively aligns the team's activities with the Social Security System's (SSS) overall strategic direction.	3.86	FM
4. Actively seeks opportunities for branch improvement and innovation.	3.93	FM
5. Promotes a culture of continuous improvement and adaptability		
General Assessment	3.89	FM
Standard Deviation	0.27	
Legend:	3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree –	Fully Manifested (FM)
	2.50 - 3.49 Agree –	Manifested (M)
	1.50 - 2.49 Disagree–	Slightly Manifested (SM)
	1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree –	Not Manifested (NM).

Public administration skills among heads of SSS Santa Rosa Branch in terms of Vision was Fully Manifested (3.89, σ -0.27) The indicators “Consistently demonstrates a strong commitment to the mission and goals of the organization” and “Actively seeks opportunities for branch improvement and innovation” yielded the highest mean of 3.93 interpreted as Fully Manifested. On the other hand, indicator “align the team's activities with the Social Security System's (SSS) overall strategic direction and promote a culture of continuous improvement and adaptability” received the lowest mean of 3.86 interpreted as Fully Manifested.

It implies that SSS heads and supervisors are aware of and fully understand the Mission, Vision, and Quality Policy of the organization. It clearly shows that they give importance to the continuous improvement of the services being rendered. A big attribute

of this is the creation of the Quality Management Department wherein they cultivate a strong mindset in focusing on quality standards, provide services within the standards and encourage continual improvement.

Krpálek et al. (2021) in their book entitled “Formation of Professional competences and Soft Skills of Public Administration Employees for Sustainable Professional Development”, emphasized that the current situation was causing changes to manifest themselves in the digitalization of management processes, components of knowledge management, and the transmission of global threats. Soft skills were becoming increasingly in demand. The more the employer needed for competence, the more frequently it was employed by employees, and the higher the workers' assessment of their ability. At the same time, they had a stronger demand for this skill and were eager to train it. In the case of executives, a substantial tendency had been discovered. Soft skills were most used, and employees wanted to learn more about them. Project management training had the least interest. Digital systems were the most utilized and required professional competencies. The study outlined trends in the development of new technology, digitalization, and information systems that helped public administrators perform more effectively. Soft skill development for both rank-and-file and executive staff was required.

Manaf et al. (2020) in their book entitled “Differences in Personality and the Sharing of Managerial Tacit Knowledge: An Empirical Analysis of Public Sector Managers in Malaysia” aimed to discover differences in knowledge-sharing processes and personality among expert, typical, and novice managers in Malaysia's public sector. Improving the function of information exchange is critical for enabling public institutions all around the world to be more productive. The findings showed that expert managers were more proactive in sharing their expertise, particularly those with conscientiousness and openness as personality qualities. These two personality traits were also linked to expert behaviors including thoroughness, responsibility, and persistence, which resulted in job competency and managerial success.

1.2 Philosophy

Public administration skills among heads of SSS Santa Rosa Branch in terms of Philosophy was Fully Manifested (3.86 σ -0.30). The indicator “instills a sense of accountability and responsibility among branch employees” yielded the highest mean of 3.93 interpreted as Fully Manifested. On the other hand, “consistently promotes a customer-centric philosophy within the branch received the lowest mean of 3.79 interpreted as Fully Manifested.

Table 1.2

Level of Manifestation of Public Administration Skills among Heads of SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by Employees and Clients in terms of Philosophy

Indicators	X	VI
The Branch Head & Supervisors of SSS Santa Rosa is ...		
1. Dedicated to upholding ethical standards and integrity in all aspects of branch operations	3.86	FM
2. Consistently promotes a customer-centric philosophy within the branch	3.79	FM
3. Actively supports diversity and inclusion initiatives, ensuring a fair and equitable workplace	3.86	FM
4. Emphasizes transparency and open communication in decision-making processes	3.86	FM
5. Instills a sense of accountability and responsibility among branch employees	3.93	FM
General Assessment	3.86	FM
Standard Deviation		
Legend:	3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree –	Fully Manifested (FM)
	2.50 - 3.24 Agree –	Manifested (M)
	1.75 - 2.49 Disagree–	Slightly Manifested (SM)
	1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree –	Not Manifested (NM).

It implies that when employees feel a strong sense of accountability and responsibility, they are more productive, make better decisions, and work together more effectively. The emphasis on accountability and responsibility implies that SSS Santa Rosa's leadership is committed to cultivating a culture of professionalism and dedication, which contributes to overall service quality and operational efficiency.

On the other hand, a customer-centric philosophy is essential for any service-oriented organization because it prioritizes meeting customer needs and providing excellent service experiences. The implication that this aspect is lacking may indicate a disconnect between leadership priorities and frontline staff, insufficient training or resources for customer service, or a lack of emphasis on customer satisfaction within the organizational culture. In contrast to the previously mentioned high level of accountability and responsibility, the lack of a strong customer-centric philosophy may indicate a weakness in the branch's ability to effectively meet its client's needs and expectations, potentially leading to decreased customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Kruyen and Van Genugten (2020) in their book entitled "Opening up the black box of civil servants' competencies" found that employee abilities were critical to understanding individual performance. Using the findings of a survey of public officials, they analyzed which competencies were valued in government. To some extent, these competencies can be linked to three major governance philosophies: traditional Public Administration, New Public Management, and New Public Governance, but several other

meaningful clusters of competencies can also be distinguished, including creativity-related competencies and self-development skills. Based on our findings, we draw lessons for civil servants and public (human resource) management.

1.3 Excellent Leadership

Table 1.3

Level of Manifestation of Public Administration Skills among Heads of SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by Employees and Clients in terms of Excellent Leadership

Indicators	X	VI
The Branch Head & Supervisors of SSS Santa Rosa is ...		
1. Effectively delegates responsibilities and empowers team members to contribute their best.	3.79	FM
2. Demonstrates strong interpersonal skills, fostering a positive and collaborative work environment.	3.86	FM
3. Provides constructive feedback and recognizes employees for their achievements.	3.64	FM
4. Is adept at conflict resolution and handles challenging situations with professionalism.	3.71	FM
5. Continually invest in the professional development of branch employees, promoting a culture of learning.	3.71	FM
General Assessment	3.79	FM
Standard Deviation	0.28	
Legend:	3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree –	Fully Manifested (FM)
	2.50 - 3.24 Agree –	Manifested (M)
	1.75 - 2.49 Disagree–	Slightly Manifested (SM)
	1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree –	Not Manifested (NM).

Public administration skills among heads of the SSS Santa Rosa Branch in terms of Excellent Leadership were Fully Manifested (3.79, σ - 0.28). The indicator “continually invests in the professional development of branch employees, promoting a culture of learning” got the highest mean score of 3.93 interpreted as Fully Manifested. On the other hand, “provides constructive feedback and recognizes employees for their achievements” got the lowest mean score of 3.64 interpreted as Fully Manifested.

It implies that continually investing in branch employees' professional development and promoting a learning culture demonstrates a strong commitment to employee growth and organizational excellence. By putting professional development first, leadership fosters a skilled and knowledgeable workforce capable of adapting to challenges and providing high-quality service. This investment demonstrates a proactive approach to employee retention and engagement, as well as an understanding of the value of continuous learning in a dynamic workplace. Such a commitment to professional development is associated with increased employee satisfaction, productivity, and overall performance.

On the contrary, giving constructive feedback and recognizing employees' accomplishments, on the other hand, indicates a weakness in critical aspects of employee management. Constructive feedback and recognition are critical components of effective leadership and employee engagement. Employees who do not receive adequate feedback may struggle to understand their performance expectations or areas for improvement, stifling professional development and overall productivity. Similarly, recognition is critical for reinforcing positive behavior and creating a culture of appreciation and acknowledgment in the workplace. The absence or inadequacy of feedback and recognition mechanisms may result in disengagement, low morale, and, ultimately, lower employee performance and satisfaction levels.

Alvarenga et al. (2020) pointed out that digitizing public services was currently a critical requirement for many governments throughout the world. A better government as a result of digitalization will not only have a rising impact on businesses, but it will also be able to increase citizen engagement and push for economic progress. The findings indicated that research on the topic was still in its early stages due to a paucity of studies linking digital government to knowledge management efficacy in the public sector. The findings also indicated that the success of digital government appeared to be tied to the quality of the organizations' knowledge management, with the two contributing to major advances in the public sector. In terms of novelty, this study aimed to add to and inspire data-driven discussions about the effects of digital transformation in the public sector and their relationship with knowledge management practice adoption. The findings provided insight into future research needs.

1. 4 Customer Service

Public administration skills among heads of the SSS Santa Rosa Branch in terms of Customer Service were Fully Manifested (3.86, σ - 0.20). The indicator “promotes a customer-centric mindset among branch employees and the Branch Head & Supervisors of SSS Santa Rosa is dedicated to ensuring a high level of customer satisfaction within the branch”. got the highest mean of 3.93 interpreted as Fully Manifested. On the other hand, “actively seeks feedback from customers and uses it to improve service delivery” got the lowest mean of 3.71 interpreted as Fully Manifested.

Table 1.4

Level of Manifestation of Public Administration Skills among Heads of SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by Employees and Clients in terms of Customer Service

Indicators	X	VI
The Branch Head & Supervisors of SSS Santa Rosa is ...		
1. Is dedicated to ensuring a high level of customer satisfaction within the branch.	3.93	FM
2. Actively seeks feedback from customers and uses it to improve service delivery.	3.71	FM
3. Promotes a customer-centric mindset among branch employees.	3.93	FM

4. Implements initiatives to reduce customer wait times and streamline service processes.	3.86	FM
5. Fosters a culture of empathy and responsiveness when addressing customer inquiries or concerns.	3.86	FM
General Assessment	3.86	FM
Standard Deviation	0.20	
Legend:	3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree– 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree –	Fully Manifested (FM) Manifested (M) Slightly Manifested (SM) Not Manifested (NM).

It implies a strong commitment to prioritizing customers in their service delivery. By instilling such a mindset, they are likely emphasizing the importance of understanding and responding to customer needs quickly and effectively. While promoting a customer centric mindset is admirable and contributes to a positive service culture, it may not always result in concrete actions or improvements unless customer feedback is actively utilized.

Mugellini et al. (2021) mentioned that the field of collaborative public management research was thriving. The method and impact of collaboration in the public sector were receiving a lot of attention, and the outcomes were positive. This article examined the literature on collaborative public administration by combining what they knew from recent studies as well as what they had known for a long time. It discussed the recent and historical popularity of collaboration, the components of new collaborative structures, the types of abilities that were particular to collaborative management, and the effects of collaboration. Collaborative public management research provided a set of findings that contributed to a growing body of knowledge that supplemented established public management theory.

Research Question 2.

What is the service delivery level in SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by clients and employees in terms of:

2.1 Accuracy of Service

Table 2.1

Service Delivery Level in SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by Employees and Clients in terms of Accuracy of Service

Indicators	Employees		Clients		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The SSS Santa Rosa Branch	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. Consistently precise in processing and recording client information.	3.64	VG	3.67	VG	3.66	VG
2. Reliable and error-free in the accuracy of	3.57	VG	3.57	VG	3.57	VG

Benefit calculations.						
3. Processed correctly the clients' documents with full trust.	3.64	VG	3.63	VG	3.64	VG
4. Maintains high accuracy in handling financial transactions for its clients.	3.86	VG	3.58	VG	3.72	VG
5. Ensures that all client records are updated and maintained with precision.	3.71	VG	3.60	VG	3.66	VG
General Assessment Standard Deviation	3.69 0.31	VG	3.61 0.48	VG	3.65	VG
Legend:	3.25 - 4.00 Very Satisfactory- Very Good (VG), 2.50 - 3.24 Satisfactory- Good (G), 1.75 - 2.49 Slightly Satisfactory- Fair (F), 1.00 - 1.74 Unsatisfactory- Poor (P)					

The SSS Santa Rosa Branch's Accuracy of Service was Very Good (3.65, σ -0.31, 0.48) The indicator "maintains high accuracy in handling financial transactions for its clients", got the highest composite mean of 3.72 and was interpreted as Very Good. On the contrary, "reliable and error-free in the accuracy of benefit calculations" got the lowest composite mean of 3.57 interpreted as Very Good.

It implies that the branch's ability to manage financial transactions is accurate. This could be attributed to the staff's meticulousness and precision when dealing with clients' financial matters. Clients are likely to appreciate the branch's commitment to processing transactions accurately, which contributes to a positive overall experience.

Norona et al. (2020) found the number of complaints about the quality of service provided by Philippine government entities has been increasing. Even though various research and ideas have been adopted in this area, gaps between service providers and their customers remain. This study intended to evaluate these gaps and confirm precise relationships among its factors, notably for the country's top non-performing agency. The framework was created through rigorous data verification, with most of the information coming from employee and consumer answers, as well as confirmation on related references. As a result, the level of client satisfaction was discovered to be strongly dependent on the agency's ambiance, working hours, transaction queue, and people's talent.

2.2 Perceived Quality

Table 2.2

Service Delivery Level in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by Employees and Clients in terms of Perceived Quality

Indicators	Employees		Clients		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The SSS Santa Rosa Branch						
1. Easily accessible, providing convenient Operating hours for clients.	3.71	VG	3.61	VG	3.66	VG
2. Clients find that there is sufficient service counters open at SSS Santa Rosa Branch to minimize waiting time.	3.57	VG	3.50	VG	3.54	VG
3. Consistently maintains a full staff to handle client inquiries and requests promptly.	3.64	VG	3.56	VG	3.60	VG
4. Online services provided are available 24/7 for client convenience.	3.50	VG	3.50	VG	3.50	VG
5. Offers alternative communication channels, ensuring availability even during peak hours.	3.57	VG	3.55	VG	3.56	VG
General Assessment	3.60	VG	3.54	VG	3.57	VG
Standard Deviation	0.40		0.49			
Legend:						
	3.25 - 4.00	Very Satisfactory- Very Good (VG),				
	2.50 - 3.24	Satisfactory- Good (G),				
	1.75 - 2.49	Slightly Satisfactory- Fair (F),				
	1.00 - 1.74	Unsatisfactory- Poor (P)				

The SSS Santa Rosa Branch's Perceived Quality was Very Good (3.57, σ -0.40, 0.49). The indicator "easily accessible, providing convenient operating hours for clients" got the highest composite mean of 3.66 interpreted as Very Good. On the other hand, "online services provided are available 24/7 for client convenience" got the lowest mean score of 3.50 verbally interpreted as Very Good.

It implies that the SSS Santa Rosa Branch's accessibility and convenient operating hours greatly contribute to its clients' high level of satisfaction. Ease of access implies that clients prefer to visit the branch in person, and the extended operating hours accommodate a variety of schedules. This could be attributed to a well-planned location and a customer-centric approach, which ensures that clients can easily access the branch's services with minimal inconvenience.

Masiya et al. (2019) found that community frustration with basic municipal service delivery was increasing in emerging nations such as South Africa. Many academics suggested that the growth in service delivery demonstrations in South Africa can be related to organizations' failure to offer adequate basic services, while many communities

remained unserved. This article studied and analyzed citizen satisfaction with basic municipal service delivery in South Africa using the South African Social Attitude Survey. The investigation was quantitative in character. The findings showed that perceptions of relative deprivation and inequality, unfulfilled political promises, uneven access to services, provision of substandard services, and high levels of poverty, including post-apartheid disparities, all influenced citizen dissatisfaction with service delivery. The article was timely because many African municipalities faced comparable service delivery issues.

2.3 Prompt Feedback

The SSS Santa Rosa Branch’s Prompt Feedback was Very Good (3.59, σ -0.38, 0.49). The indicator “promptly responds to client inquiries and concerns” got the highest assessment score of 3.70 verbally interpreted as Very Good. On the contrary, “clients consistently experience a rapid response to their feedback, showcasing the branch's commitment to service improvement” got the lowest assessment score of 3.54 verbally interpreted as Very Good.

Table 2.3

Service Delivery Level in SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by Employees and Clients in terms of Prompt Feedback.

Indicators	Employees		Clients		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The SSS Santa Rosa Branch						
1. Promptly responds to client inquiries and concerns.	3.79	VG	3.61	VG	3.70	VG
2. Clients receive timely updates on the status of their application at SSS Santa Rosa Branch.	3.50	VG	3.59	VG	3.55	VG
3. Feedback from clients is actively sought and addressed promptly by the branch.	3.6	VG	3.52	VG	3.58	VG
4. Ensures quick resolution of issues raised by Clients through efficient communication channels.	3.64	VG	3.51	VG	3.58	VG
5. Clients consistently experience a rapid response to their feedback, showcasing the branch’s commitment to service improvement.	3.57	VG	3.50	VG	3.54	VG
General Assessment	3.63	VG	3.55	VG	3.59	VG
Standard Deviation	0.38		0.49			
Legend:	3.25 - 4.00 Very Satisfactory- Very Good (VG), 2.50 - 3.24 Satisfactory- Good (G), 1.75 - 2.49 Slightly Satisfactory- Fair (F), 1.00 - 1.74 Unsatisfactory- Poor (P)					

It implies that clients receive prompt responses when they contact the branch. This high level of satisfaction is due to efficient customer service practices, effective communication channels, and a commitment to responding to client needs quickly. On the contrary, it could imply that, despite the branch's responsiveness, there are underlying issues or concerns that are adequately addressed.

According to Engdaw (2019), customer happiness was critical in sustaining and improving the reputation of a public service organization. Customers who were satisfied with the service were more inclined to promote it to others, which can lead to increased public trust and support for the organization. Dissatisfied consumers, on the other hand, may communicate their unfavorable experiences, resulting in a tarnished reputation and lower public faith in the service given.

2.4 Physical Safety

Table 2.4

Service Delivery Level in SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by Employees and Clients in terms of Physical Safety

Indicators	Employees		Clients		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The SSS Santa Rosa Branch	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1.Provides a safe and secure environment for clients and staff.	3.43	VG	3.62	VG	3.53	VG
2. Adequate safety measures are in place to prevent accidents or incidents within the branch premises	3.50	VG	3.55	VG	3.53	VG
3. Clients feel secure when visiting the SSS Santa Rosa Branch due to visible safety protocols.	3.57	VG	3.60	VG	3.59	VG
4.Conducts regular safety drills to ensure preparedness for emergencies.	3.64	VG	3.49	VG	3.57	VG
5.The physical layout is designed to prioritize the safety and wellbeing of both clients and staff.	3.50	VG	3.55	VG	3.53	VG
General Assessment Standard Deviation	3.53	VG	3.56	VG	3.55	VG
Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Very Satisfactory- Very Good (VG), 2.50 - 3.24 Satisfactory- Good (G), 1.75 - 2.49 Slightly Satisfactory- Fair (F), 1.00 - 1.74 Unsatisfactory- Poor (P)						

The SSS Santa Rosa Branch's Physical Safety was Very Good (3.55, σ -0.45, 0.49). The indicator "conducts regularly safety drills to ensure preparedness for emergencies" got the highest assessment score of 3.59 verbally interpreted as Very Good. On the other hand, SSS Santa Rosa Branch "provides a safe and secure

environment for clients and staff, the SSS Santa Rosa adequate safety measures are in place to prevent accidents or incidents within the branch premises” and the “SSS Santa Rosa Branch’ physical layout is designed to prioritize the safety and well-being of both clients and staff” got the lowest assessment score of 3.53 interpreted as Very Good.

This implies that the emphasis on regular safety drills indicates a commitment to preparedness and an understanding of the value of training in handling emergencies effectively. This commitment to ongoing training implies that the SSS Santa Rosa Branch takes a comprehensive approach to safety, relying not only on static measures but also actively engaging in practices that improve the overall safety culture. However, they do reveal a potential gap between perceived safety measures and client and staff satisfaction. While the branch provides a safe and secure environment and claims to have adequate safety measures in place, the mention of the physical layout being designed for safety suggests that the effectiveness of these measures may be compromised.

Moreover, Vu (2021) revealed that customer satisfaction was an important statistic for assessing the effectiveness of government service delivery. Organizations can discover areas for development and make educated decisions to improve service quality by assessing customer happiness. Customer feedback can provide significant insights into the service's strengths and flaws, allowing for continual improvement initiatives.

2.5 Comfortability

The SSS Santa Rosa Branch’s Comfortability was Very Good (3.61, σ -0.35, 0.47). The indicator “clients find the staff to be friendly and accommodating, enhancing overall comfort” got the highest assessment score of 3.77 interpreted as Very Good. On the other hand, the “SSS Santa Rosa Branch environment is well-maintained, contributing to a pleasant and comfortable atmosphere” got the lowest assessment score of 3.46 interpreted as Very Good.

Table 2.5

Service Delivery Level in SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by Employees and Clients in terms of Comfortability

Indicators	Employees		Clients		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The SSS Santa Rosa Branch	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. Creates a welcoming and comfortable waiting area for clients.	3.50	VG	3.63	VG	3.57	VG
2. Adequate seating and facilities are provided to ensure a comfortable experience for clients.	3.50	VG	3.56	VG	3.53	VG
3. Environment is well-maintained, contributing to a pleasant and comfortable atmosphere.	3.36	VG	3.55	VG	3.46	VG
4. Clients find the staff to be friendly and accommodating, enhancing overall comfort.	3.93	VG	3.61	VG	3.77	VG

5. Takes measures to minimize waiting times, contributing to a more comfortable experience for clients.	3.86	VG	3.56	VG	3.71	VG
General Assessment Standard Deviation	3.63 0.35	VG	3.58 0.47	VG	3.61	VG
Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Very Satisfactory- Very Good (VG), 2.50 - 3.24 Satisfactory- Good (G), 1.75 - 2.49 Slightly Satisfactory- Fair (F), 1.00 – 1.74 Unsatisfactory- Poor (P)						

Research Question 3

Is there a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of public administration skills and service delivery in SSS Santa Rosa Branch?

Table 3

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Manifestation of Public Administration Skills and Service Delivery in SSS Santa Rosa Branch.

Manifestation of Public Administration	Service Delivery in SSS	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Vision and Commitment	Accuracy	0.2530	0.3830	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Availability	0.3180	0.2680	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Feedback	.5848*	0.0280	Significant	Reject Ho
	Physical Safety	0.4920	0.0740	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Comfortability	.3980	0.1580	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Philosophy	Accuracy	.773**	0.0010	Significant	Reject Ho
	Availability	.620*	0.0180	Significant	Reject Ho
	Feedback	0.4160	0.1390	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Physical Safety	.555*	0.0400	Significant	Reject Ho
	Comfortability	.663**	0.0100	Significant	Reject Ho
Excellent Leadership	Accuracy	.730**	0.0030	Significant	Reject Ho
	Availability	.622*	0.0200	Significant	Reject Ho
	Feedback	.613*	0.0200	Significant	Reject Ho
	Physical Safety	.749**	0.0020	Significant	Reject Ho
	Comfortability	.736**	0.0030	Significant	Reject Ho
Customer Service	Accuracy	.810**	0.0000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Availability	.619*	0.0180	Significant	Reject Ho
	Feedback	0.5020	0.0680	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Physical Safety	.559*	0.0380	Significant	Reject Ho
	Comfortability	.683**	0.0070	Significant	Reject Ho

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

There was a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of public administration skills and service delivery in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch, vision, and prompt feedback. There was a significant relationship between philosophy and accuracy, philosophy and availability, philosophy and physical safety, and philosophy and comfortability. There was a significant relationship between excellent leadership and service delivery, as well as customer service and service delivery. The r values are all between 0.510 to 0.75 which indicates High Positive Correlation. The probability values of 0.0280, .0.0010, 0.0180, 0.040, 0.0100, 0.0030, 0.0200, 0.0030, 0.000, 0180 .03800 and 0.0070 respectively were less than the level of significance at .05, thus, rejecting the null hypothesis.

On the other hand, there was no significant relationship between the manifestation of public administration skills such as vision and accuracy, vision and availability, vision and physical safety, vision and comfortability, philosophy, and prompt feedback. The probability values are greater than the level of significance at .05, thus, accepting the null hypothesis.

This means that when the public administration skills level increases, service delivery also increases, when the public administration skills level decreases, service delivery level also decreases. For a variety of reasons, Dave et al. (2022) said that consumer happiness was crucial to the quality of public services.

For starters, satisfied customers were more likely to have a favorable assessment of the public service provided. Customers who were pleased with the service were more likely to regard it as dependable, efficient, and effective. This positive perception fostered trust and credibility between the public service provider and its clients.

Research Question 4

What is the SSS Santa rosa Branch members' trust and confidence in public administration in its services in terms of:

4.1 Assurance

Table 4.1

SSS Santa Rosa Branch Members' Trust and Confidence in Public Administration in its Services in terms of Assurance

Indicator	Employees		Clients		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The SSS Santa Rosa Branch						
1. Is transparent in communicating policies and procedures to members, ensuring they fully understand their rights and entitlements	3.79	VH	3.62	VH	3.71	VH

2.Members feel secure about the confidentiality of their personal information when interacting with SSS Santa Rosa Branch.	3.79	VH	3.56	VH	3.68	VH
3.Staff demonstrate a high level of competence and knowledge, providing accurate and reliable information to members.	3.79	VH	3.58	VH	3.69	VH
4. Members trust that it adheres to ethical Standards, ensuring fair and unbiased treatment in all interactions.	3.79	VH	3.53	VH	3.66	VH
5. Effectively communicates its commitment to member satisfaction and continuous improvement in service delivery.	3.86	VH	3.66	VH	3.76	VH
General Assessment Standard Deviation	3.80 0.35	VH	3.59 0.58	VH	3.70	VH
Legend:	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree-	Very High (VH),			
	2.50 - 3.24	Agree-	High (H),			
	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree	Low (L),			
	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Very Low (VL)			

The SSS Santa Rosa Branch members' trust and confidence in its services in terms of Assurance was Very High (3.70, σ -0.35, 0.58) "The SSS Santa Rosa Branch effectively communicates its commitment to member satisfaction and continuous improvement in service delivery" and got the highest assessment score of 3.76 interpreted as Very High. On the contrary, the "SSS Santa Rosa Branch members trust that it adheres to ethical standards, ensuring fair and unbiased treatment in all interactions" got the lowest assessment score of 3.66 interpreted as Very High.

It implies that the branch excels at building positive relationships with its members by consistently demonstrating its dedication to meeting their needs. The emphasis on continuous improvement suggests a proactive approach to addressing member concerns and meeting changing service expectations. On the contrary, while members are not as satisfied overall, there was a level of trust in the branch's ethical conduct, which ensures fair and unbiased treatment in all interactions. The emphasis on ethical standards implies that, even if service satisfaction is less than ideal, members believe in the branch's integrity and expect fair and just treatment.

Tuncer et al. (2021) found that the concept of client loyalty had grown in popularity in recent years. Customer loyalty was regarded as critical to a company's success by both academics and practitioners. Developing client loyalty was another technique that was well suited to the service industry because services provided more opportunities for such growth. Nonetheless, despite the obvious relevance of client loyalty to all organizations, particularly service businesses, there was still much to be learned. The goal of this study was to use structural equation modeling to examine the impact of service quality, satisfaction, and trust on consumer loyalty to the service provider. The findings of an

empirical study on travel agents showed how client pleasure and trust influence loyalty. In turn, service quality influenced satisfaction. Most past research had focused on quality and satisfaction, but in this study, they added trust to the list of characteristics that predicted loyalty. The findings further supported the SERVQUAL scale's applicability to the travel agency industry and highlighted the existence of the five aspects stated by the original authors. This added to the ongoing discussion over the dimensionality of service excellence.

4.2 Empathy

Table 4.2

SSS Santa Rosa Branch Members' Trust and Confidence in Public Administration in its Services in terms of Empathy

Indicators	Employees		Clients		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The SSS Santa Rosa Branch						
1. Is known for its empathetic and understanding approach when addressing members' concerns or challenges.	3.86	VH	3.63	VH	3.75	VH
2. Staff actively listen to members, showing genuine concern for their individual needs and circumstances.	3.86	VH	3.52	VH	3.69	VH
3. Members feel supported and valued, experiencing a sense of compassion and empathy in their rights and entitlements.	3.79	VH	3.61	VH	3.70	VH
4. Takes a personalized approach, recognizing and considering the unique circumstances of each member.	3.79	VH	3.55	VH	3.67	VH
5. Demonstrate a patient and empathetic attitude, particularly when assisting members facing difficulties or uncertainties.	3.86	VH	3.60	VH	3.73	VH
General Assessment	3.83	VH	3.58	VH	3.71	VH
Standard Deviation	0.33		0.47			
Legend:						
	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree-	Very High (VH),			
	2.50 - 3.24	Agree-	High (H),			
	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree	Low (L),			
	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Very Low (VL)			

The SSS Santa Rosa Branch members' trust and confidence on its services in terms of Empathy was Very High (3.71, σ -0.33, 0.47). "The SSS Santa Rosa Branch is known for its empathetic and understanding approach when addressing members' concerns or challenges" got the highest assessment score of 3.75 verbally interpreted as Very High. On the contrary, the "SSS Santa Rosa Branch takes a personalized approach,

recognizing and considering the unique circumstances of each member” got the lowest mean score of 3.67 interpreted as Very High.

It implies that the SSS Santa Rosa Branch emphasizes member satisfaction and personalized service. It excels at addressing members' concerns with tact and compassion. The branch has established a reputation for providing excellent customer service and actively listening to its members' needs. The empathetic approach is likely to improve members' overall experience, fostering trust and loyalty to the institution.

Nguyen et al. (2020) investigated the correlations and effects of service quality, customer satisfaction, and switching costs on customer loyalty in commercial banks' ebanking. The findings revealed that all five e-banking service quality indicators—dependability, responsiveness, service capacity, empathy, and tangibility—had positive associations with customer satisfaction. Among these factors, service capability and tangibility had the most influence. It indicated that commercial banks can better satisfy their customers by improving the quality of their services through the five elements listed above, particularly by boosting capacity and tangibility. Furthermore, consumer happiness was highly and positively associated with customer loyalty. It indicated that if clients were satisfied with a bank's e-banking services, they would not only continue to do business with that bank but would also promote it to others. Finally, client loyalty had a high and positive association with switching costs, implying that customers were more likely to remain loyal to one bank as the obstacles to switching banks increase.

4.3 Reliability

The SSS Santa Rosa Branch members' trust and confidence in terms of Reliability was Very High (3.71, σ -0.32, 0.63). The “SSS Santa Rosa Branch members can rely on the SSS Santa Rosa Branch to efficiently process their transactions, minimizing delays and ensuring prompt service” got the highest assessment score of 3.81 verbally interpreted as Very High. On the contrary, the “SSS Santa Rosa Branch consistently meets or exceeds established service standards and commitments to members” got the lowest assessment score of 3.66 interpreted as Very High.

Table 4.3

SSS Santa Rosa Branch Members' Trust and Confidence in Public Administration in its Services in terms of Reliability

Indicators	Employees		Clients		Assessment	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The SSS Santa Rosa Branch	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. Consistently delivers accurate and timely information regarding members' contributions, benefits, and other related matters.	3.79	VH	3.63	VC	3.71	VH
2. Members can rely on the SSS Santa Rosa	3.93	VH	3.68	VC	3.81	VH

Branch to efficiently process their transactions, minimizing delays and ensuring prompt service.						
3. The accuracy of records and data maintained Instills confidence in members regarding the reliability of the information provided.	3.93	VH	3.68	VC	3.81	VH
4. Consistently meets or exceeds established service standards and commitments to members.	3.79	VH	3.53	VC	3.66	VH
5. Members have confidence in the reliability of the systems and technology used for managing their accounts and transactions.	3.79	VH	3.55	VC	3.67	VH
General Assessment	3.81	VH	3.60	VC	3.71	VH
Standard Deviation	0.35		0.63			
Legend:						
	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree-	Very High (VH),			
	2.50 - 3.24	Agree-	High (H),			
	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree	Low (L),			
	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Very Low (VL)			

This means that the SSS Santa Rosa Branch processes transactions efficiently, resulting in prompt service. This also shows that members have a positive perception of the branch's efficiency and dependability, both of which are important factors contributing to high satisfaction levels. The emphasis on efficient transaction processing demonstrates that the branch values customer service and works hard to meet members' needs as soon as possible. However, while the branch may follow certain service standards and commitments, there may be aspects of service delivery or member experience in which it falls short of meeting members' expectations. This could include things like communication, accessibility, or overall member experience, which may not meet members' preferences or needs.

Ali et al. (2021) emphasized that businesses relied on customers, and the profitability of any organization varied based on client demand. As a result, the client must be treated as the market king. In another sense, customer satisfaction was a critical issue for a company's product since it evaluated the amount of likelihood between the company's product and consumer belief, and the happier the customer with quality and types of products, the more products and profit will occur. The goal of this research was to investigate the impact of technical and functional service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty. A lot of results were gathered while conducting a survey, and the results pertain to their opinions on various types of platforms used for online meetings and academic purposes.

4.4 Responsiveness

Table 4.4

SSS Santa Rosa Branch Members' Trust and Confidence in Public Administration in its Services in terms of Responsiveness

Indicators	Employees		Clients		Assessment	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The SSS Santa Rosa Branch						
1. Promptly addresses member inquiries and concerns, providing timely and satisfactory resolutions.	3.79	VH	3.63	VH	3.73	VH
2. Members receive acknowledgment and updates on the status of their requests, ensuring transparency and keeping them	3.93	VH	3.56	VH	3.75	VH
3. Proactively seeks feedback from Members and takes prompt action to address an identified area for improvement.	3.79	VH	3.57	VH	3.68	VH
4. Staff are accessible and responsive, making it easy for members to seek assistance or clarification.	3.79	VH	3.57	VH	3.68	VH
5. Actively engages with members through various communication channels, ensuring a quick and responsive service experience.	3.86	VH	3.59	VH	3.71	VH
General Assessment	3.83	VH	3.58	VH	3.71	VH
Standard Deviation	0.35		0.47			
Legend:	3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree- Very High (VH), 2.50 - 3.24 Agree- High (H), 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree- Low (L), 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Very Low (VL)					

The SSS Santa Rosa Branch members' trust and confidence in its services in terms of Responsiveness was Very High (3.71, σ -0.35, 0.47). The "SSS Santa Rosa Branch members receive acknowledgment and updates on the status of their requests, ensuring transparency and keeping them informed" got the highest assessment score of 3.75 interpreted as Very High. On the contrary, the "SSS Santa Rosa Branch proactively seeks feedback from members and takes prompt action to address any identified areas for improvement" and the "SSS Santa Rosa Branch staff are accessible and responsive, making it easy for members to seek assistance or clarification" got the lowest mean score of 3.68 interpreted as Very High.

It implies that the branch's commitment to acknowledging and updating members on the status of their requests, fostering transparency, and keeping individuals informed

throughout the process. This commitment to communication is likely to contribute to a positive member experience by managing expectations and building trust. On the other hand, some aspects may still fall short of members' expectations. Staff accessibility and responsiveness are highlighted as positive factors, allowing members to easily seek assistance or clarification.

Wagner (2019) also suggested that service delivery firms with developed customer relationship management can track complaints and give an indication of the service quality perception of customers. Godoy (2019) also suggested the use of a gap theory to analyze service quality. The gap theory addressed service quality by analyzing the differences between customers' expected service quality and the actual service quality received.

4.5 Tangibility

Table 4.5

SSS Santa Rosa Branch Members' Trust and in Public Administration in its Services in terms of Tangibility

Indicators	Employees		Clients		Assessment	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The SSS Santa Rosa Branch						
1. Physical facilities are well-maintained and organized, contributing to a positive and professional atmosphere.	3.50	VH	3.62	VH	3.56	VH
2. Members find the documentation and materials provided to be clear, accessible, and user-friendly.	3.71	VH	3.53	VH	3.62	VH
3. Offers convenient and modern channels for members to access information and services, both online and offline.	3.79	VH	3.63	VH	3.71	VH
4. Tangible elements, such as signage and communication materials, reflect the commitment to provide quality service.	3.71	VH	3.66	VH	3.69	VH
5. Members perceive the overall physical and digital environment as conducive to a positive and efficient service experience.	3.64	VH	3.63	VH	3.64	VH
General Assessment	3.67	VH	3.61	VH		VH
Standard Deviation	0.43		0.45			
Legend:	3.25 - 4.00 Very High (VH) 2.50 - 3.24 High (H) 1.75 - 2.49 Low (L) 1.00 - 1.74 Very Low (VL)					

The SSS Santa Rosa Branch members' trust and confidence in public administration on its services in terms of Tangibility was **Very High (3.64, σ -0.43, 0.45)**. The "SSS Santa Rosa Branch offers convenient and modern channels for members to access information and services, both online and offline" got the highest assessment score of **3.71** interpreted as **Very High**. On the other hand, the "SSS Santa Rosa Branch physical facilities are well-maintained and organized, contributing to a positive and professional atmosphere" got the lowest assessment score of **3.64** interpreted as **Very High**. On the contrary, the SSS Santa Rosa Branch physical facilities are well-maintained and organized, contributing to a positive and professional atmosphere got the least mean score of **3.56** was interpreted as **Very High**.

It implies that members are very satisfied with the convenience and modern channels for accessing information and services at the SSS Santa Rosa Branch, but they are slightly less satisfied with the branch's physical facilities. The facilities are not being fixed by the lessor since the branch is about to relocate to a new office and the current building where the branch was located will undergo renovation. The system has invested in technology and streamlined its processes to make it easier for members to interact with its services. This could include online portals, mobile apps, automated kiosks, and other digital platforms that enable members to easily access information and complete transactions, the current of which is the uSSSap tay portal.

In a study conducted by Suen and Hung (2023) entitled "Building trust in automatic video interviews using various AI interfaces: Tangibility, immediacy, and transparency" they discussed that in the post-pandemic age, businesses were calling for more automated video interviews driven by artificial intelligence (AI), but there were also growing concerns about job candidates' level of trust in the technology. AI-based video interviews were used for pre-employment screening in a variety of ways, with and without the tangibility, immediacy, and transparency features. These features can have a significant impact on applicants' trust in the technology and whether they participated in the hiring process. Based on the self-reporting of 152 actual job candidates, this field study involved developing an experiment to determine how different types of AI-based video interviews affected interviewers' cognitive and affective trust.

The results of the study showed that candidates' cognitive trust was higher in the AI-AVI (asynchronous video interviewing) condition than it was in the non-AI condition. Furthermore, the applicants' cognitive and affective trust rose when the AI-AVI possessed tangibility and transparency properties. The immediacy feature, however, had no statistically significant effect. Despite worries about the possible drawbacks of AI and its characteristics, this study identified no statistically significant consequences.

Research Question 5

Is there a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of public administration skills and members' trust and confidence in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch?

Table 5

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Manifestation of Public Administration Skills and Members' Trust and Confidence on SSS Santa Rosa Branch

Manifestation of Public Administration	Members' trust and confidence on SSS	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Vision and commitment	Assurance	.845**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Empathy	.548*	0.043	Significant	Reject Ho
	Reliability	.630*	0.016	Significant	Reject Ho
	Responsiveness	.611*	0.014	Significant	Reject Ho
	Tangibility	.666**	0.009	Significant	Reject Ho
Philosophy	Assurance	.706**	0.005	Significant	Reject Ho
	Empathy	.854**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Reliability	.887**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Responsiveness	.869**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Tangibility	.740**	0.003	Significant	Reject Ho
Excellent leadership	Assurance	.823**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Empathy	.876**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Reliability	.901**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Responsiveness	.894**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Tangibility	.868**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Customer Service	Assurance	.706**	0.005	Significant	Reject Ho
	Empathy	.767**	0.001	Significant	Reject Ho
	Reliability	.792**	0.001	Significant	Reject Ho
	Responsiveness	.727**	0.003	Significant	Reject Ho
	Tangibility	.746**	0.002	Significant	Reject Ho

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

There was a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of public administration skills and members' trust and confidence in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch. As shown in the probability values all .000 which were less than the level of significance at .05. Thus, rejecting the null hypothesis. The r-values were between 0.51 to 0.99 or High Positive Correlation.

It indicates that the higher the manifestation of public administration skills the higher the members' trust and confidence in SSS Santa Rosa Branch. It implies also that competent public administration fosters trust and confidence. Transparent decision-making processes, accountability mechanisms, and responsiveness to their needs further reinforce trust. As trust increases, members are more likely to be covered by SSS and

encourage non-members to be an SSS member, comply with laws and regulations, and support public initiatives.

In connection, according to Kumar et al. (2021) in their study entitled "Building trust among channel members via power sources", building on the encapsulated interest and motivated cognition accounts, this study sought to analyze how channel members extended trust in a channel leader when the channel leader employed various non-coercive power sources (e.g., referent, expert, legitimate, and reward power). Furthermore, the study looked at how channel members' faith in a channel leader changed when non-coercive power sources were combined with coercive power sources. The findings showed that expert and reward power sources increased trust in channel leaders, whereas emotional commitment moderated the effects of all non-coercive power sources on trust. Furthermore, coercive power reduced the impact of expert authority on trust.

Research Question 6

Is there a significant relationship between the service delivery and members' trust and confidence on SSS Santa Rosa Branch?

Table 6

Test of Significant Relationship between the Service Delivery and Members' Trust and Confidence in SSS Santa Rosa Branch

Service Delivery in SSS	Members' trust and confidence	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Accuracy	Assurance	.630**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Empathy	.728**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Reliability	.581**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Responsiveness	.759**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Tangibility	.542**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
Availability	Assurance	.640**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Empathy	.764**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Reliability	.543**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Responsiveness	.735**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Tangibility	.552**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
Feedback	Assurance	.606**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Empathy	.730**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Reliability	.604**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Responsiveness	.768**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Tangibility	.541**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
Physical Safety	Assurance	.604**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Empathy	.732**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Reliability	.572**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Responsiveness	.730**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Tangibility	.564**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho

Comfortability	Assurance	.601**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Empathy	.748**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Reliability	.542**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Responsiveness	.720**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho
	Tangibility	.533**	0.00	Significant	Reject Ho

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

There was a significant relationship between the service delivery and members' trust and confidence in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch. As shown in the probability values were all .000 which was less than the level of significance at .05 Thus rejecting the null hypothesis. The r values were between 0.51 to 0.99 and indicated High Positive Correlation.

It indicates that that the higher the service delivery, the higher the members' trust and confidence in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch. Higher service delivery not only directly improves SSS members' lives but also plays a crucial role in shaping their perceptions of government effectiveness, reliability, and trustworthiness. It reinforces the social contract, fosters community well-being, and creates a positive feedback loop that strengthens the relationship between citizens and the government.

According to Hailu and Shifare (2019) in their study entitled "Service Delivery and customer satisfaction in the Public Service Sector", clients of public service organizations were generally happy with the companies' overall service performance. However, there were statistically significant service delivery discrepancies within and between each selected public sector agency. The key obstacles in public service delivery were a lack of responsibility, a readiness to give service as requested, a sense of belonging, inconsistencies in rules and regulations, and a lack of integration among various government service providers. Public service organizations should implement appropriate and realistic accountability measures, as well as consistently collaborate on the preparation of their rules, regulations, and procedures, to achieve better integration and provide good service delivery to their customers.

Research Question 7

Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

The action plan for enhancing customer-centric philosophy, improving feedback mechanisms, enhancing online services, strengthening trust and ethics, and meeting service commitments outlines a comprehensive approach to improving branch operations. The goal is to foster a culture centered around customer satisfaction and ethical conduct while ensuring seamless online services and meeting service commitments. To achieve this, the plan includes actions such as implementing customer service training, establishing feedback mechanisms, investing in IT infrastructure, conducting ethics training, and reviewing service standards. Additionally, regular audits, monitoring, and evaluation processes are in place to track progress and make necessary

adjustments. By consistently seeking feedback and refining strategies, the branch aims to continuously enhance its services and build trust with both employees and customers alike.

Table 7

Proposed Action Plan for Improving Public Administration Skills, Service Delivery, and Trust in SSS Santa Rosa Branch

KEY AREAS	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	FREQUENCY	PERSONS INVOLVED	SUCCESS INDICATOR
Customer-Centric Philosophy	To instill and consistently promote a customer-centric philosophy within the branch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Implement customer service training for all heads including rank and file employees -Post easy to be understood Citizens Charter in conspicuous place within the branch -Conduct regular customer service audits 	Semi-annually	<p>SSS Santa Rosa Management</p> <p>Learning and Development Department</p>	At least 2 trainings for all heads and personnel are conducted
Improving Feedback Mechanism	To actively seek and utilize feedback from both employees and customers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement a structured feedback collection system. Provide feedback in the counter. -Establish a cross-functional team to analyze and act upon feedback. Regularly monitor actions and compliance being done and -Recognize and reward employees for contributing to service improvement 	Quarterly	Administrative Heads	<p>A structured feedback collection has been implemented.</p> <p>A cross-functional team has been established.</p> <p>100% of the employees has been recognized and rewarded</p>

Meeting Service Commitments	Consistently meet or exceed established service level agreements	contract under the Office Performance Commitment and Review (OPCR) and Individual Performance Commitment and Review (IPCR) being the performance measurement system. -Conduct regular service quality assessments and maintain the ISO certification.	Annually	Branch Systems and Procedure Department, Corporate Policy and Planning Department	100% of the established service level agreement has been meet.
-----------------------------	--	--	----------	---	--

RESULTS

Summary of Findings

Based on the data gathered and after careful and thorough analysis of the investigation, the following are the findings of the study in summarized form.

Level of Manifestation of Public Administration Skills among Heads of the SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by Employees in terms of:

1.1 Vision

It had a general assessment of 3.89 interpreted as Fully Manifested.

1.2 Philosophy

It had a general assessment of 3.86 interpreted as Fully Manifested.

1.3 Excellent Leadership

It had a general assessment of 3.79 interpreted as Fully Manifested.

1.4 Customer Service

It had a general assessment of 3.86 interpreted as Fully Manifested.

Level of Service Delivery in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch as assessed by Clients and Employees in terms of:

2.1 Accuracy of Service

It had a general assessment of 3.65 interpreted as Very Good.

2.2 Perceived Quality

It had a general assessment of 3.57 interpreted as Very Good.

2.3 Prompt Feedback

It had general assessment of 3.59 interpreted as Very Good.

2.4 Physical Safety

It had a general assessment of 3.55 interpreted as Very Good.

2.5 Comfortability

It had a general assessment of 3.61 interpreted as Very Good.

3. Test of Significant Difference between the Assessment of the Heads and Employees on the Level of Manifestation of Public Administration Skills among Heads of the SSS Santa Rosa Branch

There was a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of public administration skills and service delivery in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch, vision, and prompt feedback. There was a significant relationship between philosophy and accuracy, philosophy and availability, philosophy and physical safety, and philosophy and comfortability. There was a significant relationship between excellent leadership and service delivery, as well as customer service and service delivery. The r values are all between 0.510 to 0.75 which indicates High Positive Correlation. The probability values of 0.0280, .00010, 0.0180, 0.040, 0.0100, 0.0030, 0.0200, 0.0030, 0.000, 0.180 .03800 and 0.0070 respectively were less than the level of significance at .05, thus, rejecting the null hypothesis. On the other hand, there was no significant relationship between the manifestation of public administration skills such as vision and accuracy, vision and availability, vision and physical safety, vision and comfortability, philosophy, and prompt feedback. The probability values are greater than the level of significance at .05, thus, accepting the null hypothesis.

Level of SSS Santa Rosa Branch Members' Trust and Confidence on Public Administration on its Services in terms of:

4.1 Assurance

It had a general assessment of 3.70 interpreted as Very High.

4.2 Empathy

It had a general assessment of 3.71 interpreted as Very High.

4.3 Reliability

It had a general assessment of 3.71 interpreted as Very High.

4.4 Responsiveness

It had a general assessment of 3.71 interpreted as Very High.

4.5 Tangibility

It had a general assessment of 3.64 interpreted as Very High.

5. Test of Significant relationship between the Level of Manifestation of Public Administration Skills and Service Delivery in SSS Santa Rosa Branch

There was a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of public administration skills and members' trust and confidence in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch. As shown in the probability values all .000 which were less than the level of significance at .05. Thus, rejecting the null hypothesis. The r-values were between 0.51 to 0.99 or High Positive Correlation.

6. Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Manifestation of Public Administration Skills and Members' Trust and Confidence in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch

There was a significant relationship between the service delivery and members' trust and confidence in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch. As shown in the probability values were all .000 which was less than the level of significance at .05. Thus rejecting the null hypothesis. The r values were between 0.51 to 0.99 and which indicated High Positive Correlation.

7. Proposed Action Plan

As an output, an action plan was proposed to address issues on public administration skills, service delivery, and trust and confidence and serve as a guide for the leaders to be more effective.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. That SSS Santa Rosa's leadership emphasizes continuous improvement, professionalism, and employee growth through initiatives like the Quality Management Department and professional development programs. However, they may fall short in providing adequate constructive feedback and recognition to employees, which could impact performance and engagement. While prioritizing customer service is commendable, it needs active utilization of customer feedback for tangible improvements.

2. That the SSS Santa Rosa Branch excels in accurate financial transactions and convenient accessibility, leading to high client satisfaction. However, occasional errors in benefit calculations may cause dissatisfaction. Prompt responses to client inquiries indicate efficient customer service, but there may be underlying issues to address. The emphasis on service improvement and safety drills reflects a commitment to continuous enhancement, although there might be a gap between perceived and actual safety measures. Positive interactions with staff greatly enhance the customer experience, while the environment's role in satisfaction appears secondary.

3. That when the public administration skills level increases, service delivery also increases, when the public administration skills level decreases, service delivery level also decreases.

4. That the SSS Santa Rosa Branch prioritizes member satisfaction through continuous improvement and personalized service. While members trust the branch's ethical conduct, overall satisfaction levels may vary. Efficient transaction processing and proactive communication contribute to positive experiences. However, despite efforts to meet service standards, some members feel their expectations aren't fully met, particularly regarding physical facilities. The branch's emphasis on modern channels for accessing services is appreciated, but dissatisfaction with current facilities highlights areas for improvement as the branch relocates.

5. That the level of public administration skills directly correlates with members' trust and confidence in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch. Competent administration fosters trust, as members believe in the agency's ability to fulfil its mandate. Transparent decision-making and responsiveness further reinforce trust, leading to increased coverage and support for public initiatives. Investing in professional development and promoting excellence in public administration is crucial for enhancing service delivery, trust, and effective governance.

6. That there was a substantial link between the service delivery and members' trust and confidence in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch. This also indicates that the higher the service delivery, the higher the members' trust and confidence in the SSS Santa Rosa Branch. There was a strong correlation between the quality-of-service delivery and the level of trust and confidence members have in SSS.

7. That the action plan for enhancing customer-centric philosophy, improving feedback mechanisms, enhancing online services, strengthening trust and ethics, and meeting service commitments outlines a comprehensive approach to improving branch operations.

Recommendations

Based on the findings summarized and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. The SSS Santa Rosa Branch may implement regular training and development programs for heads and employees focusing on enhancing their understanding of quality standards, customer service techniques, and continuous improvement methodologies. This may further empower employees to consistently deliver high-quality services aligned with the organization's Mission, Vision, and Quality Policy.
2. The SSS Santa Rosa Branch may develop a comprehensive feedback mechanism that actively solicits input from both customers and employees. Utilize this feedback to pinpoint areas for improvement in service delivery and member satisfaction. Regularly analyze feedback data to identify trends and implement actionable solutions.
3. The SSS Santa Rosa Branch may recognize the growing importance of online service delivery channels. They may invest in developing user-friendly interfaces and functionalities to cater to evolving client preferences. This can ensure that digital interactions are seamless, secure, and accessible, reflecting a commitment to meeting client needs in today's digital landscape.
4. The Branch head may commit to ongoing investment in employee training and development programs. He/She may provide avenues for constructive feedback, recognition, and career advancement opportunities and empower employees with the skills and competencies needed to deliver exceptional service and adapt to changing customer expectations effectively.
5. The SSS Santa Rosa Branch may conduct a comprehensive assessment of the current infrastructure and facilities, considering factors such as cleanliness, accessibility, comfort, and professional ambiance. Following this assessment, they may prioritize investments in infrastructure upgrades, renovations, and modernization efforts aimed at creating a more positive and welcoming environment for members during in-person interactions. Additionally, they may consider implementing a regular maintenance schedule to ensure the sustained upkeep of the physical facility. Furthermore, they may actively seek feedback from members regarding their experience with the branch's physical facility and incorporate their suggestions and concerns into improvement initiatives.
6. The SSS Santa Rosa Branch may adopt the proposed action plan of this study to improve branch operations.
7. Future researchers may consider conducting similar investigations in their respective branches so they may find out how their branches are performing.

Acknowledgments

The findings of this study truly inspire the researcher. Although it was difficult and exhausting work, the result was invaluable. The work of the researcher would not have been possible without the assistance, guidance, and providence of the Heavenly Father, the Almighty God from whom all knowledge and wisdom originate.

The researcher would like to use this opportunity to convey her heartfelt gratitude to those who have provided words of hope, laugh-inducing jokes, advice, solutions,

comments, and suggestions, as well as shared their time and effort before and after the development of this research. These are the people who, in some manner, have made an impact on her life that she will remember and be grateful for;

Dr. Ma. Lorena M. Tagala, for her consistent direction, expert suggestions and advice in the field of research, sincere supervision and help during the study's conduct, and for raising the standard of quality education to generate competent and compassionate graduates;

Dr. Ramir R. Larino, the researcher's adviser, for his guidance, support, understanding, and effort in assisting the researcher;

Dean Alfred G. Perez, Jr., for his kindness, unwavering encouragement, and support to carry on with this study despite all hardships, obstacles and hindrances;

Dr. Eulalia M. Javier, the researcher's statistician, for offering statistical treatment for the study as well as tables for interpreting data in their questionnaires, and for her kind words and good heart;

Dr. Chester Alexis C. Buama, for his words of wisdom that provided great impact and inspiration to the researcher, for assisting, recommending, and providing comments to improve the study and make it well-crafted and correspond to the requirements;

VP Engr. Edwin Igharas, the head of SSS Luzon South I Division, for giving approval in the conduct of this study in Santa Rosa Branch;

SSS Santa Rosa Branch, for wholeheartedly accommodating and assisting during the research;

Crismon Deada, for his kindness in sharing constructive and valuable materials in this research;

Her devoted family- Loi, the researcher's better half, for the love and encouragement, children- Agatha Kristine, Justine Mae, twin- Gracielle Lhoi and Rochelle Lhoi, Michael Loi and sons-in-law- Norman Gayle, Christopher, Ka Dandy and Ka Mark Angel, for their physical and spiritual support through prayers, words of encouragement and for contributing to the success of the researcher's work.

Grandchildren- Callia Kirsten, Sir Chase Kaden, Sofia Christine Mae, Sasha Celine, Shaun Christopher, Zion Isaac Dylle, Zaven Elijah Dylle and Graymark Erron, the source of happiness and inspiration of the researcher and for elevating the researcher's mood whenever she feels low.

Siblings- Soraya, Ambro, Rainier, Danilo, Charmaine, Don and Charles Andrew and her mother Lilia, for the unconditional love.

GRV

REFERENCES

- Ali, B. J., Saleh, P. F., Akoi, S., Abdulrahman, A. A., Muhamed, A. S., Noori, H. N., & Anwar, G. (2021, May). Impact of service quality on the customer satisfaction: Case study at online meeting platforms. In Ali, BJ, Saleh, Akoi, S., Abdulrahman, AA, Muhamed, AS, Noori, HN, Anwar, G.(2021). Impact of Service Quality on the Customer Satisfaction: Case study at Online Meeting Platforms. *International journal of Engineering, Business and Management* (Vol. 5, No. 2, pp. 65-77).
- Alvarenga, A., Matos, F., Godina, R., & CO Matias, J. (2020). Digital transformation and knowledge management in the public sector. *Sustainability*, 12(14), 5824. Ana

- Fontoura Gouveia, Amílcar Moreira, Politics of Aging and Interest Groups, Encyclopedia of Gerontology and Population Aging, 10.1007/978-3-030-22009-9_240, (3868-3876), (2022).
- BallotPedia (n.d.). The Study of Administration" by Woodrow Wilson (1887). [https://ballotpedia.org/"The_Study_of_Administration"_by_Woodro](https://ballotpedia.org/)
- Catam, B. C. A. (2022). Case unclosed: Clients' and clinicians' perspectives on premature termination in psychological services. (Master's Thesis), Laguna College of Business and Arts, Calamba City.
- CPPD Management Reports (2024). Social Security System. sssph.sharepoint.com/PPDManagementReports/Facts%20and%20Figures%202024%2007%20Tentative%20FS%20rundate%200801.pdf
- Dave, I., Gupta, R., Rizve, M. N., & Shah, M. (2022). Tclr: Temporal contrastive learning for video representation. *Computer Vision and Image Understanding*, 219, 103406.
- Deada, C.T. (2020). Electronic-service quality of My.Sss portal facility and its impact on satisfaction of the Social Security System Members, San Pedro Branch
- Del Signore, A. (2024). Multiple-Award Winner Trupanion's Approach to Pet Insurance and Customer Care. The Stevie Awards. <https://blog.stevieawards.com/blog>
- Engdaw, B. D. (2020). The impact of quality public service delivery on customer satisfaction in Bahir Dar city administration: The case of Ginbot 20 sub-city. *International journal of public administration*, 43(7), 644-654.
- Godoy, O. (2019). Coexistence theory as a tool to understand biological invasions in species interaction networks: Implications for the study of novel ecosystems. *Functional Ecology*, 33(7), 1190-1201.
- Hailu, A. G., & Shifare, H. G. (2019). Service delivery and customer satisfaction in the public service sector: An Ethiopian experience. *Public Policy and Administration*.
- Kotler, P., Pfoertsch, W., Sponholz, U., Kotler, P., Pfoertsch, W., & Sponholz, U. (2021). The current state of marketing. *H2H Marketing: The Genesis of Human-to-Human Marketing*, 1-28. (2021). Formation of professional competences and soft skills of public administration employees for sustainable professional development. *Sustainability*, 13(10), 5533.
- Krpálek, P., Berková, K., Kubišová, A., Krelová, K. K., Frencliovská, D., & Spiesová, D. (2021). Formation of Professional Competences and Soft Skills of Public Administration Employees for Sustainable Professional Development. *Sustainability 2021*, 13(10), 5533; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13105533>
- Kruyen, P. M., & Van Genugten, M. (2020). Opening up the black box of civil servants' competencies. *Public Management Review*, 22(1), 118-140.
- Kumar, S., Jebarajakirthy, C. & Das, M. (2021), Building trust among channel members via power sources. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, ISSN: 0885-8624
- Manaf, A.H., Harvey, W. S., Armstrong, S. J., & Lawton, A. (2020). Differences in personality and the sharing of managerial tacit knowledge: an empirical analysis of public sector managers in Malaysia. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 24(5), 1177-1199.
- Masiya, T., Davids, Y. D., & Mangai, M. S. (2019). Assessing service delivery: Public perception of municipal service delivery in South Africa.
- Mugellini, G., Della Bella, S., Colagrossi, M., Isenring, G. L., & Killias, M. (2021). Public sector reforms and their impact on the level of corruption: A systematic review. *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, 17(2), e1173.
- Nguyen, D. T., Pham, V. T., Tran, D. M., & Pham, D. B. T. (2020). Impact of service quality, customer satisfaction and switching costs on customer loyalty. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(8), 395-405.
- Norona, M. I., Louise, T., & Evangelista, L. (2020, April). An Ergonomics-ServQual Approach in Enhancing the Service Delivery Performance for a Government Agency in the

- Philippines. In 2020 IEEE 7th International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Applications (ICIEA) (pp. 303-306). IEEE.
- Pastrana, N. (2022). Social Support And Psychological Well-Being Among Omsc Cte Students During The Pandemic. *International Journal of Educational Research and Social Sciences (IJERSC)*, 3(2), 798-803.
- Reyes, G., Comson, A., Hernandez, M. B., Vigonte, F., & Abante, M. V. (2023). Demographic variables as predictor of member satisfaction: a comprehensive assessment report on the Social Security System (SSS) service quality. Available at SSRN 4623139.
- Shafritz, J. M., Russell, E.W., Borick, C. P., & Hyde, A. C. (2022). *Defining Public Administration*. Routledge. eBook ISBN9781003191322
- Suen, H.Y., & Hung, K.E. (2023). Building trust in automatic video interviews using various AI interfaces: Tangibility, immediacy, and transparency. *Computers in Human Behavior*, Volume 143, June 2023, 107713. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2023.107713>
- Tuncer, I., Unusan, C., & Cobanoglu, C. (2021). Service quality, perceived value and customer satisfaction on behavioral intention in restaurants: An integrated structural model. *Journal of quality assurance in hospitality & tourism*, 22(4), 447-475.
- Uzir, U. H., Halbusi, H. A., Thurasamy, R., Hock, R. L. T., Aljaberi, M. A., Hasan, N., & Hamid, M. (2021). The effects of service quality, perceived value and trust in home delivery service personnel on customer satisfaction: Evidence from a developing country. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Volume 63, November 2021, 102721. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2021.102721>
- Vu, T. P. (2021). Port service quality (PSQ) and customer satisfaction: an exploratory study of container ports in Vietnam. *Maritime Business Review*, 6(1), 72-94.
- Wagner, S. (2019). Perceived quality, authenticity, and price in tourists' dining experiences: Testing competing models of satisfaction and behavioral intentions. *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 25(4), 480-498.